

An Analysis of Adult Syrian Refugees' Opinions on Turkish Courses Opened in Cooperation with the United Nations and the Ministry of National Education¹

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Abstract: In this study, it is aimed to examine adult Syrian refugees' opinions on the Turkish courses opened in cooperation with the UN and the Ministry of National Education in Türkiye. A basic qualitative research method was used in the study. The study group of the research consisted of 18 adult Syrian refugees attending the courses in Public Education Centre. The data were collected through focus groups. Content analysis was used to analyze the data. As a result of the analyses various conclusions were reached: reasons for the participation of adult Syrian refugees in the courses, the relationship of the course content with daily life, the difficulties encountered, the actions taken to solve these difficulties, and suggestions for the development of the course program.

Key Words: Adult Syrian Refugees, Turkish Courses, Language Training, Language Learning; Qualitative Research

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1. Introduction

The civil war that started in Syria in 2011 displaced millions of Syrians and triggered a massive wave of migration to neighboring countries. Türkiye has been one of the countries to receive the largest number of Syrian refugees in this process. According to the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR), there are approximately 3.7 million Syrian refugees in Türkiye as of 2023 (UNHCR, 2023). This massive wave of migration has led to significant changes in Türkiye's social, economic, and cultural structure, and the integration of refugees into education and social life has become one of the most important items on the country's agenda.

Language education plays a fundamental role in integrating refugees into education and social life. Language directly affects individuals' participation in society, employment, and educational opportunities (Bourdieu, 1991). According to the European Commission for Education and Culture (2007), communication in the mother tongue and in foreign languages are among the competencies of lifelong learners. In the context of Syrian refugees' integration into Turkish society, Turkish language learning is of great importance. For them, knowing Turkish is a tool to continue their lives in Türkiye, to receive education, to

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find a job, and most importantly to communicate with people in daily life (Seydi, 2014, p. 276). However, the process of learning Turkish by adult Syrian refugees brings with it various difficulties and problems. The most fundamental of these is the language barrier. The grammatical structure and pronunciation features of Turkish are quite different from Arabic, which makes the language-learning process of adult Syrian refugees difficult (Ünal, Taşkaya, & Ersoy, 2018). The lack of a sufficient number of language courses in some regions or the limited capacity of existing courses also stands out as an important obstacle (Morali, 2018). Many adult refugees work for long periods to earn a living and therefore do not have enough time to attend language courses (Nimer, 2019). Although some courses are free of charge, additional costs such as language course fees, transportation to the course, and material costs can also negatively affect participation in language courses (Kaya, 2020). Psychological and emotional difficulties caused by war and forced migration experiences can also reduce adult Syrian refugees' motivation to learn a language and slow down their learning process (İçduygu, 2021). Family responsibilities (especially for women refugees - such as childcare and housework) may limit the time available for language courses (Akkaya, 2013, Büyükkız and Çangal, 2016). Factors such as insufficient educational materials and pedagogical problems faced by teachers in language teaching can also be listed among these challenges (Er, Biçer, & Bozkırlı, 2012; Gözübüyük Tamer, 2020; Nimer, 2019).

Various institutions and organizations carry out language training programs for adult Syrian refugees in Türkiye. (UNDP, 2023). In particular, the European Union (EU) funded the "Resilience Project in Türkiye in Response to the Syria Crisis (TDP) - Turkish Language Training for Adults", implemented in partnership with the Ministry of National Education, Directorate General of Lifelong Learning and United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), was launched on 25 March 2019 in 53 Public Education Centers (PECs) in ten provinces of Türkiye (Adana, Bursa, Gaziantep, Hatay, Istanbul, Izmir, Kilis, Konya, Mersin, and Şanlıurfa). More than 70,000 Syrian adults have benefited from this training to support their economic, social, and cultural participation. Through these trainings, Syrian refugees between the ages of 18 and 57 have been empowered socially and economically and have contributed to social and cultural cohesion. In these training, A1, A2, and B1 level training were provided within the scope of the four basic language skills specified in the European Language Portfolio. Seventy-five percent of the participants were women. These courses were delivered through blended learning environments. For face-to-face training, 316 master trainers were assigned and trained, and for distance learning environments, a learning management system was established that participants could easily use and access at any time and place (UNDP, 2024).

In addition to supporting the social cohesion and integration of refugees, language education increases their employment opportunities and facilitates their daily lives (Nimer, 2019; Fejes, Chamberland and Sultana, 2022; Svensson, 2023). From this perspective, the implementation of qualified language courses for refugees in a host country significantly impacts their integration into social life. Language skills enhance refugees' abilities to communicate in daily life, access education and employment opportunities, and thereby strengthen their participation and sense of belonging in society. Therefore, examining the course from the participants' perspectives helps to refine the curriculum, provides valuable

feedback on content and materials, identifies inefficiencies, and ultimately establishes the foundation for a well-developed curriculum. Furthermore, participant feedback ensures that essential components such as cultural sensitivity and the specific needs of refugees are integrated, making the curriculum more inclusive. In this way, a well-developed curriculum can be expected to dismantle barriers to integration, allowing Syrian refugees to experience a sense of unity with the society in which they reside. For this reason, this study aims to examine adult Syrian Refugees' views on the Turkish language courses organized in cooperation with the UN and MoNE. In line with this purpose, answers to the following questions were sought:

Syrian refugees attending Turkish courses organized in cooperation with the UN and MoNE;

- What is the purpose of attending this course?
- What are their views on the relevance of the content presented in the course to their daily lives?
- What are their opinions about the learning-teaching process of the course?
- How did the course affect their daily communication skills?
- What are the difficulties they experienced during the course?
- What are their suggestions about the program of the course?

2. Method

In this section, the research model, study group, data collection tools, data collection, data analysis, and ethical principles in research are given.

Research Model

In the study, "basic qualitative research", one of the qualitative research method designs, was used. Basic qualitative research is concerned with how people interpret their lives, how they construct their worlds and how they give meaning to their experiences (Merriam, 2009). In this study, a basic qualitative research design was preferred since it was aimed to reveal the opinions of adult Syrian refugees and course instructors about the Turkish courses opened in cooperation with the UN and MoNE through their own experiences.

Study Group

The study group of the research was formed by affinity sampling. Affinity sampling is one of the purposeful sampling methods and is a type of sampling used in studies where similar phenomena or groups are investigated (Patton, 2002). The common characteristic of the participants who make up the study group of this research is that they are adult Syrian refugees participating in Turkish courses opened in cooperation with the UN and MoNE.

The study group of the research consists of a total 18 adult Syrian refugees attending Turkish courses. They were coded as M1, M2.

Among the adult Syrian refugees who participated in the courses, 3 were male and 15 were female. According to age groups; 6 of them are between 18-24 years old, 4 of them

are between 25-29 years old, 4 of them are between 30-34 years old, 1 of them is between 35-39 years old and 3 of them are 40 years old and above. According to the duration of their residence in Türkiye, 1 of the Syrian refugees residing in Türkiye is between 0-1 year, 1 is between 1-3 years, 5 is between 3-5 years, 8 is between 5-8 years and 3 is 8 years and above. According to whether the Syrian refugees participated in the study received Turkish education before attending the course or not; 12 of them did not, while 6 of them receive Turkish education before attending the course.

Data Collection Tool

Interview form was used as data collection tool in the study. To prepare the interview questions, the literature was reviewed and an interview form was prepared for adult Syrian refugees. The draft questions were submitted to the opinion of experts in the field of curriculum and instruction. To check the grammatical accuracy and comprehensibility of the questions, the opinions of two experts, one of whom is a Turkish teacher and the other an Arabic teacher, were obtained. Interview form questions were organized in line with the feedback from the experts. Pilot interview was conducted with one person who had similar characteristics to the characteristics of the study group, and necessary arrangements were made on the interview form. There were 9 open-ended questions in the interview form.

Collection of Data

Data were collected through focus group interviews with adult Syrian refugees. The focus group interviews with the trainees were conducted in six separate focus groups of three participants each. The interviews were conducted in Arabic, the native language of the participants, so that the participants could express themselves more easily. The data were translated from Arabic into Turkish (after being checked for grammatical accuracy and comprehensibility by field experts who know Turkish and Arabic) and written down.

The research data were collected face-to-face and audio-recorded at the Public Education Center for Syrian refugees who volunteered to take language courses at the Public Education Center. The interviews were held in the meeting room of the relevant public education center in a round table arrangement so that the members could interact with each other. Audio recording and written consent were obtained from the participants by the researcher who interviewed before the interview started.

Ethical Principles in Research

The ethics committee permission for the research was obtained from the Anadolu University Ethics Committee Commission with the official letter dated September 30, 2021 and numbered 211698. For the implementation of the research, permission for the application and survey study was obtained from the Bursa Provincial Directorate of National Education with an official letter dated December 4, 2021, and numbered 40445755.

During the data collection process, the researchers first informed the participants in detail about the nature of the research by making the necessary explanations. The participants signed the "Voluntary Participation Form" and their written consent was obtained for the research. The processes of conducting the interviews, analyzing, and reporting the data were also carried out by the researchers.

Data Analysis

The content analysis was conducted using the qualitative data analysis program MAXQDA 2018 with the analysis stages used by Thomas and Harden (2008) (coding the findings, developing descriptive themes, generating analytical themes, and ensuring credibility and consistency).

To ensure the consistency of the data analysis in the study, the data were analyzed by a field expert other than the researcher, and a consensus was tried to be reached. Miles and Huberman's (1994) consistency formula was used to calculate the consensus. As a result of the analysis, the consensus between the researcher and the field expert was found to be .80. Miles and Huberman (1994) stated that the consistency of research results of .70 and above is high.

3. Findings

When the findings obtained from the focus group interviews with adult Syrian refugees participating in the courses were analyzed, seven main themes were formed. These main themes are as shown in Figure 1:

Figure 1. Main Themes

The reasons why adult Syrian refugees attend Turkish courses are thematized as:

Figure 2. Reason/Purpose for Participation

Some examples of participant responses to the sub-themes are given below:

"I want to adapt to Turkish society, to be able to express my complaint properly when I go to the hospital, to be able to communicate with my children's teachers at school, to be able to do my shopping in government institutions without needing an interpreter. If we live here, we need to learn the language of this society. Because they do not have to learn our language. I have met refugees who have been living in Türkiye for 8 years or more and do not know Turkish. I have been living here for 4 years and I always wanted to learn it until I attended this course." (Improving Turkish Communication/Language Skills; Taking Part in Children's Education, Adapting to Society) (M7)

" My second goal is to improve my Turkish to get the equivalence of the diploma I received it from Syria. Because I need to take some exams and those exams will be conducted in Turkish. " (Institutional Documentation and Registration) (M3)

Opinions of adult Syrian refugees about Turkish language is thematized as follows:

Figure 3. Opinions on Language

Some examples of participant responses to the codes of the Easy Aspects sub-theme are given below:

"Turkish is a bit difficult, but since it contains many words of Arabic origin, it gives me an advantage and makes learning easier." (Finding Arabic Origin Words) (M12)

"Turkish is considered an easy language compared to other languages, especially for someone who knows Latin and English letters, I think they will find it easier." (Learning Turkish Compared to Other Languages) (M2)

Some examples of participant responses to the codes of the Difficult Aspects sub-theme are given below:

"There are many idioms and phrases in Turkish and most of them are used metaphorically. For example, 'we ate the quince' has a different meaning here, it means to be in a difficult situation and to get into a dead end, not to eat the quince" (Vocabulary/Linguistic Learning) (M13)

"I had a lot of difficulty at first, now my ear is more familiar and the thing I have the most difficulty with is pronunciation, I understand all of what they say, but I can't speak, I can't progress when I speak, I keep saying ee ee ee." (Speaking/Pronunciation) (M3)

The opinions of adult Syrian refugees on the relationship between the content offered in the course and daily life are thematized as follows:

Figure 4. The Relationship between Course Content and Daily Life

Some examples of participant responses to these sub-themes are given below:

"There are useful topics in the content. For example, it teaches us phrases and sentences used in places such as restaurants, museums, and bazaars. If we use these, I think our Turkish will undoubtedly be more beautiful." (The Content is Related to Daily Life; Being Effective in Social Communication) (M5)

"The information in the book does not really help us to adapt to the society. Especially for us, refugees, I wish it was more refugee-oriented and included examples of the difficulties they face." (Content Not Related to Daily Life) (M17)

Opinions of adult Syrian refugees on the teaching process offered in the course thematized as shown in Figure 5:

Figure 5. Opinions on the teaching process

Some examples of participant responses to the sub-theme of Teaching Skills (f=22) are given below:

"The teacher explains the lesson to us in a very simple and understandable way, she tries to speak clearly" (Instruction Appropriate to Readiness Level) (M8)

"The vocabulary guide in the book is very good, where the most used words are selected and listed. Especially on weekends, they give us time to complete the test within that time. This way we learn from our mistakes and it's a lot of fun. Even if the activity ends, we can access them again and correct and reinforce what we have learned." (Enabling Self-Paced Learning) (M9)

Some examples of participant responses to the sub-theme of Classroom Environment are given below:

The classroom environment; cleaning, lighting, painting, desks are as they should be." (Appropriate Physical Structure of the Classroom) (M2)

"The desks were small, they put children's desks and we really couldn't fit in." (Inappropriate Physical Structure of the Classroom) (M2)

Some examples of participant responses to the sub-theme of Tools and Equipment are given below:

"The teaching process was very good, the projection was used and there was an application that the teacher made us use...When the projection was used, we could learn the meaning of words we did not know by looking at pictures and visuals. The teacher made us practice the subjects we were studying by quizzing with Kahoot." (Projection; Web 2.0 Applications) (M2)

Opinions of adult Syrian refugees on the difficulties they face during the course are thematized as follows:

Figure 6. Challenges Encountered

Some examples of participant responses to these sub-themes are given below:

"I have difficulty in knowing the meaning of new words. I learn and apply the rule in grammar, but when I encounter new words in another sentence, I cannot apply the rule. New words need to be added and the books need to be enriched." (Vocabulary/Glossary Learning) (M14)

"When I didn't understand something, I didn't know how to explain to the teacher what I didn't understand. When someone talks to me, I get nervous and hesitate." (Inability to Express oneself in the Target Language) (M2)

"Sometimes I am late for class or I can't come. The reason for this is my children. I have 7 children. Some of them have school and get sick. When they are absent, I feel like I am coming to class for the first time." (Family-related Problems) (M7)

"The biggest challenge I face is that the teacher is Turkish and we trainees are Arab. Our languages are completely different. My teacher also had no knowledge of my language...." (Teachers' ignorance of students' mother tongue) (P3)

The opinions of adult Syrian refugees on the solution of the problems they face during the course process were thematized as shown at Figure 7:

Figure 7. Actions taken to solve the problems encountered

Some examples of participant responses to the sub-themes are given below:

"When I go home, I try to watch YouTube videos of the lessons I have taken, I have a notebook for myself and I write down the new words I have learned. I look at them again from there and I also get help from my children who go to school. I also benefit from the books of my children who go to primary school." (Individual Learning Methods; Family Support) (M7)

"I use the digital dictionary. I look at it to find out the meaning of a word or how it is written. I also attend a Turkish course remotely, the teacher knows both Arabic and Turkish, and he explains the words we do not understand immediately." (Language Learning with Web 2.0 Tools; Participation in Different Courses) (M6)

"I made Turkish friends, they help me, if there is something I don't know, I ask them for help." (Peer Support) (M17)

Opinions of adult Syrian refugees on the improvement of their ability to communicate using Turkish in their daily lives after the courses they took thematized as follows:

Figure 8. Development status of communication skills

Some examples of participant responses to these sub-themes are given below:

"I understand very well what the Turks are saying, but unfortunately it is very difficult to explain. It is difficult to express, speak, write. Before, when my neighbor used to say hello to me, I used to say hello back and pass by. Now, when we meet, our conversation lasts longer, thanks to the course, I can now fill in the forms requested in government institutions easily. But of course I cannot participate in deep discussions." (Impact on Language Skills [Listening Skills; Speaking Skills]; Socio-Cultural Communication Skills) (M7)

"Honestly, I started to understand more easily after attending the course, especially when someone speaks to me, I can now distinguish the tense of the verbs they use, whether they use the past tense, future tense, present tense. I use Turkish more appropriately and construct sentences more appropriately, for example, before I always used the imperative tense, now I use the request tense. Thus, the other party understands me better and feels comfortable with me 'can you come to my place?'" (Impact on

Language Skills [Listening Skills; Speaking Skills]; Socio-Cultural Communication Skills) (M1)

The expectations of adult Syrian refugees from the course are thematized as:

Figure 9. Expectations

Some examples of participant responses to these sub- themes are given below:

"To improve speaking skills, to find a job, to get the equivalence of the diploma, to adapt, to express to the society without making pronunciation mistakes." (Improving Turkish Language Skills; Economic Expectations, Academic Progress) (M2)

"To improve my literacy skills, to help my children at school, and most importantly, when I encounter a problem, to be able to explain it in a comfortable way to the other party, especially we are refugees here, sometimes I get comments from the environment about us coming to Türkiye and I cannot give a response and I would be very uncomfortable." (Improving Turkish Language Skills; Academic Progress, Gaining Socio-Cultural Skills) (M3)

"To find a job." (Economic Expectations) (M3)

"I will enroll in an open secondary school, and since there are no teachers there, I need to have Turkish first so that I can study." (Academic Progress) (M12)

The suggestions of adult Syrian refugees for the improvement of the course program are thematized as follows:

Figure 10. Suggestions for Improving the Course Program

Some examples of participant responses to these sub-themes are given below:

"The level of the students in the class should be similar and close to each other, the trainees with good level should be placed in a separate class and the trainees with poor level should be placed in a separate class to increase speaking activities Even if it is one day a week, it should be arranged for speaking practice" (Curriculum and Activities According to Individual Differences) (M1)

"I think it would be better if the teacher had an interpreter with him/her when he/she gives a new topic, but we cannot come to the course because there is no place where we can leave our children. Turkish education centers should be increased." (Bringing Course Centers Closer to Trainees) (M11)

"There should be evening courses, especially for working people who can only attend these courses after work. It would make it easier for students to learn if the Turkish teacher is interested in or knows a little bit about the language of the foreign students, let's say Arabs. The grouping of the students should be determined by giving them a test and determining their needs before taking them to a separate course for the older and younger students. I mean, some of them have Turkish, some know the letters, some can read." (Instructor's Knowledge of Refugees' Mother Tongue; Course Hours; Curriculum and Activities According to Individual Differences; Differentiation of Teaching Methods and Techniques) (M1)

4. Discussion

In this study, the quality of the Turkish courses opened in cooperation with the UN and MoNE was analyzed in the context of the opinions of the adult Syrian refugees who attended the courses. In this section, the results obtained at the end of the research are discussed by comparing the opinions of adult Syrian refugees and evaluating them in light of the studies in the literature.

Regardless of legal status, age, profession, and country of origin, the most fundamental issue that concerns all migrants is housing, followed by language learning. While migrants who learn the language of the country migrate to make rapid progress in many areas such as education, health, finding a job, solving bureaucratic problems, cultural and social adaptation, and establishing a sense of belonging, those who do not learn the language may face various problems in all areas of life. For this reason, countries that constantly receive immigration develop new policies to utilize the energy of the immigrant population, to ensure that they contribute to the economy, and to prevent a possible social explosion. One of these policies is language teaching. In the study, it was determined that the reasons/purposes of adult Syrian refugees' participation in Turkish courses are primarily to improve their Turkish communication/language skills and to adapt to society. Similar studies in the literature also support this result. Kandemir (2018) and Köse and Özsoy (2018) found that correct and effective language teaching can accelerate the adaptation of immigrants to society and essentially change their characteristics of being a burden on society and turn them into individuals who add energy to societies. Karaman (2018), in his research on Syrian refugees, determined that language courses play a key role in social cohesion and sociocultural transformation and accelerate their participation in language and culture, and thus in society and business life. In the study conducted by Akarçay (2021), the reasons for foreign students to learn Turkish were listed as working, getting to know the culture, and getting an education. In the study conducted by Orhan (2019), it was determined that the need to communicate was at the forefront among the reasons for learning Turkish, followed by individual interests and needs, education and job opportunities, and the need to trade.

According to the results of the research, the trainees stated that the easy aspects of the Turkish language are the presence of words of Arabic origin and the enjoyment of learning Turkish. It can be said that Turkish will be easy to learn in languages and cultures with which we have historical, religious, and cultural ties and with which we exchange words. For example, leaving aside the difference in alphabets, Arab and Iranian students are familiar with some words in Turkish. It can be said that the similarity in languages generally reflects positively on teaching (transfer). It can be predicted that many cognates living in different geographies will learn Turkish more easily since they are already familiar with the structure of Turkish. However, it should be said that this view is partially correct. In the study conducted by Kurt (2017) with the members of Gagauz Turkish, which is the closest dialect to Türkiye Turkish, it was concluded that the students' comprehension (reading and listening) skills were quite successful, while their expression (speaking and writing) skills were at an average level. Based on this example, it can be said that typological similarity reflects positively on comprehension skills and negatively on expression skills. A similar relationship also exists in English, German and French. In the

study, it was observed that adult Syrian refugees stated that the presence of Arabic-origin words in Turkish and the enjoyment of learning the language are the easy aspects of the language.

The trainees evaluated the difficult aspects of Turkish language as vocabulary/grammar learning and speaking/pronunciation (especially pronunciation of vowels). Similarly, in the study conducted by Bölükbaş (2016) with Syrians, vocabulary/grammar learning and speaking/pronunciation were evaluated as difficult aspects of Turkish language. Again, in the studies conducted by Nimer (2019) and Koçak (2022), it was found that trainee Syrian refugees had difficulties in learning Turkish grammar. Similarly, in the study conducted by Phutkaradze (2018) in which the language needs of immigrants for Turkish language teaching were determined, it was determined that immigrants had difficulties in grammar and speaking.

When we look at the process of teaching foreign languages in general and Turkish as a foreign language in particular, individuals are expected to be able to use the language they have learned effectively in their daily lives in line with their goals. In the study, it was determined that the majority of adult Syrian refugees stated that the course content was related to daily life and effective in social communication, while some participants, albeit a small number, stated that the relationship of the content with daily life was limited. Similarly, in the studies conducted by Gözübüyük Tamer (2020), Yıldız and Sertoğlu (2019) and Boylu and Çal (2018) in the literature, it was determined that the language needs of refugees are to be able to communicate in their daily lives, to provide social interaction, to help their children at school, and to be able to easily handle their work in the market, hospital and government institutions in daily life.

In the study, it was determined that adult Syrian refugees experienced difficulties such as vocabulary/language knowledge learning, communication skills and inability to express themselves in the target language, speech/pronunciation, and family-related problems. Similar studies in the literature also support this result. In a study conducted by Kuşcu (2014) with foreign nationals, it was found that the most difficult issue for individuals while learning Turkish was the grammatical structure of Turkish language. It was stated that Turkish is difficult with its suffixed structure and different alphabet compared to their mother tongue. One of the difficulties encountered is lack of motivation. In a study conducted by Acat and Demiral (2002), lack of motivation was stated as the most important problem that individuals experience while learning Turkish. According to the study conducted by Yıldız and Ramanenkava (2020) to determine the language needs of Belarusian students in teaching Turkish as a foreign language, motivation was seen as very important in the context of individual interest. Alyılmaz (2018) also emphasized the importance of individuals' motivation and attitudes towards language in teaching Turkish as a foreign language. In the studies conducted by Boylu and Çal (2018) and Aydoğdu, Aydoğdu, and Asmaz (2019) with Syrian refugees, it was concluded that it is important to determine the characteristics of the target audience, especially their vocabulary, while teaching Turkish to Syrian refugees.

In the study, it was determined that adult Syrian refugees developed individual learning methods to solve the problems they encountered during the course process,

practiced language learning with Web 2.0 tools and websites, received support from peers and family in language learning, and participated in different courses. Yıldız and Tepeli (2014) conducted a needs analysis on language education in the field of teaching Turkish to foreigners. The predominance of people with no expertise and the negative diversity created by the inclusion of graduates of different disciplines as the focus of their research makes "the adequacy of the teaching and learning outcomes of the field of Turkish to foreigners in terms of quality" questionable. They stated that the aforementioned instructors raise questions about "what kind of a road map they follow in terms of general and specific objectives, content, methods and techniques, materials to be used and evaluation dimensions in the processes of teaching Turkish as a foreign language or as a second language and what common ground they share". According to this result, when the educational backgrounds, fields of study and specialization of the people who work as instructors in the field of teaching Turkish to foreigners with permanent, paid and assignment procedures are taken into consideration, it can be easily said that the educational and work area outputs of the instructors do not overlap with the requirements of the field of teaching Turkish to foreigners, which has its own competencies. In their study, Kara, Yiğit, and Ağırman (2020) suggested improving the quality and quantity of the materials used for the problems faced by 15 Turkish language instructors working in temporary education centers in Batman province, increasing the interest of the trainees in Turkish, creating a curriculum in accordance with the levels of the trainees, improving the personal rights of Turkish language instructors working in projects for foreigners and providing them with the opportunity to work as permanent staff.

In the study, the results regarding the effect of the courses on the language skills of adult Syrian refugees were determined as communication in accordance with grammar rules, socio-cultural communication skills and support to the family in language. In the study conducted by Güzel and Barın (2013), it was stated that the classroom/course environment is important in terms of where individuals directly encounter various rules of Turkish. Because what is learned in the classroom/course must be used in daily life - in transportation, shopping, hospital, museum, canteen, restaurant, etc. - and thus reinforced. Raising awareness of individuals about the importance of this reinforcement is important for teaching Turkish. Another important detail is that individuals should not use their language in the classroom and the only language of communication should be Turkish. For each individual, the support of his/her family for his/her education is very important, but refugee families have various problems in supporting their children's education. The traumas experienced by family members prevent them from providing the necessary support. In addition, parents do not grasp the language of the host country as quickly as their children, making it difficult for them to share information with them. In addition to this, Strelakova and Hoot (2008) examined the importance of cultural differences between the country of immigration and the host country and their effects on individuals. According to the results of the study, it was found that cultural differences can be challenging for individuals. For example, while the concept of family loyalty is understood differently for the individual nourished by the host country's cultural norms, children's attitudes may be disrespectful and wrong for their parents who see things from their own cultural framework. Therefore, it would make the process more efficient if teachers, especially the students' teachers, were aware of such differences and ensured that families were directly involved in the education.

In addition, in a similar study conducted by Qin (2008), parents with different ethnic backgrounds were found to change their attitudes on issues such as gender roles, child rearing and marriage, while trying to maintain their attachment to their pre-migration culture.

The adult Syrian refugees stated their expectations from the course as improving their Turkish language skills and gaining socio-cultural skills, economic expectations and academic progress. Yıldız and Sertoğlu (2019) found that the resident foreigners living in Fethiye want to learn Turkish in order to communicate with people and live comfortably; Deliktaş (2019) found that the language needs of the trainees were to communicate with Turks and to receive education in Türkiye; Çelik and İpek (2019) found that the language learning needs of trainees learning Turkish in Poland were communication, trade, education and job opportunities. Similarly, in the study conducted by Kavi (2019), the sources of motivation of students learning Turkish as a foreign language were determined as communication and educational needs.

The suggestions of the adult Syrian refugees for the development of the course program were determined as; curriculum and activities according to individual differences, differentiation of teaching methods and techniques, regulations regarding the course centers, increasing the number of courses, bringing the course centers closer to the trainees, course hours and the instructor's knowledge of the mother tongue of the refugees. Phutkaradze (2018) conducted a language needs analysis of irregular migrants and revealed that a program that can be applied to these masses should be structured according to the individualized needs of the participants and that these trainings should be provided by an expert staff, teaching materials should be designed in accordance with the purpose and participant characteristics, and a content consisting of topics that will improve daily communication skills should be included. In the study conducted by Arslan (2009), it was stated that the teaching methods and materials used in teaching Turkish as a foreign language activities are important in terms of motivating individuals. Again, Er, Biçer, and Bozkırlı (2012) evaluated the problems encountered in teaching Turkish by examining the research articles on this subject in the literature. Particularly, as curriculum-related problems, it was emphasized that curricula should be prepared by considering the European Language File, that the prepared curricula should be oriented to the needs of students, that there is a need for common curricula prepared by experts, and that there are insufficient class hours.

5. Recommendations

Depending on the results obtained in this part of the study, some suggestions for practice and for researchers were developed.

Recommendations for practice

- Turkish courses should be organized for the adaptation and inclusion of migrants, some of whom were initially thought to be temporary but have become permanent, into the workforce.

- Courses should be made attractive, especially for women and children, and cultural and social integration courses should be organized alongside Turkish language courses.
- An umbrella organization should be established to ensure that all courses are accredited and that the same students do not benefit from different courses over and over again.
- Instructors need to receive special training (in-service training) for foreign/second language teaching.
- In order for the courses to be more efficient, it can be said that if a diction course is added to the programs, there will be an improvement in the trainees' speaking skills in particular.

Recommendations for researchers

- A similar study can be conducted with refugees and instructors living in different provinces.
- Similar studies can be conducted using different methods and data collection tools.
- Turkish language courses organized by different institutions and organizations for Syrian refugees can also be examined.

5. References

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